

Mechanical Behaviours in High Velocity Tension of Composites

K. Kawata, S. Hashimoto, N. Takeda

Institute of Interdisciplinary Research, Faculty of Engineering, University of Tokyo, 4-6-1 Komaba, Meguro-ku, Tokyo 153, Japan

ABSTRACT

Experimental procedure of one bar method for high-velocity tensile testing is established for obtaining dynamic stress-strain diagrams up to the breaking strain. Several composites are characterized in high-velocity tension of strain rate of about 10^3 s^{-1} . High-velocity brittleness and ductility are found in CFRP and GFRP, respectively. This is similar to high-velocity brittleness and ductility in BCC and FCC metals. Dynamic fracture mechanical considerations can also be made with circumferentially V-notched specimens. Moreover, one bar method is revised to have the capability of low-temperature testing, which enables us to study mechanical properties of materials under much wider conditions.

INTRODUCTION

The fact that higher loading velocities are often encountered in various recent advanced structures urges the study of mechanical properties in high velocity tension of materials. Based upon a series of high-velocity tension tests of various metallic materials, new concepts of high-velocity brittleness and ductility have been introduced (1, 2). They have been found closely related with the crystal lattice systems of metallic materials. High-velocity brittleness appears for BCC metals, high-velocity ductility for FCC metals, and both high-velocity brittleness and ductility for HCP metals. For material characterization in high-velocity tension, not in Charpy- or Izod-type impact testing, a precise stress-strain measuring system is required. The authors have developed a new high-velocity tensile testing method (3), that is "one bar method" which certifies no apparent oscillation in stress-strain diagrams, different from those obtained by conventional systems. In the interim report (4) using this new method, high-velocity brittleness and ductility has also been found in composite materials (CFRP and GFRP). In the present paper, first the authors summarize high-velocity tensile behaviours of composite materials. Then, with circumferentially V-notched specimens, dynamic fracture mechanical considerations are made. The application of one bar method to low-temperature impact testing is also described.

A HIGH VELOCITY TENSILE TESTING METHOD---ONE BAR METHOD

Among several possible testing methods, one bar method of block-to-bar type

has been adopted as a simple and precise one and two types of testing machines have been constructed using a rotating disc or a pendulum as a loading part (3, 4). The fundamental system of one bar method is shown in Fig. 1. Dynamic tensile stress $\sigma(t)$ and strain $\epsilon(t)$ in the specimen are calculated based upon the measured strain $\epsilon_g(t)$ from semiconductor gauges located at a distance a from the end of the output bar. The formulae for $\sigma(t)$ and $\epsilon(t)$ obtained using the one-dimensional stress wave propagation theory are as follows (3, 4):

$$\sigma(t) = (S_0/S) E_0 \epsilon_g(t + a/c) \tag{1}$$

$$\epsilon(t) = \frac{1}{l} \int_0^t [V(\tau) - c \epsilon_g(\tau + a/c)] d\tau \tag{2}$$

where l and S are length and cross-sectional area of the specimen, and S_0 , E_0 and c are cross-sectional area, Young's modulus and longitudinal wave velocity of the output bar. $V(t)$ is the velocity of the impact block. A block diagram for calculating dynamic stress and strain is shown in Fig. 2. The major feature of this testing machine is that dynamic tensile stress-strain curves are obtained up to the breaking strain immediately after tests.

Fig. 1. Fundamental System of One Bar Method.

Fig. 2. Block Diagram for Calculating Dynamic Stress and Strain.

HIGH VELOCITY TENSILE BEHAVIOURS OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

Straight Specimens

First, high-velocity tension tests using straight specimens shown in Fig. 3 (a) is conducted. As shown in Table 1, tested materials cover ten different kinds of composite materials. They are divided into three groups, that is, glass/polyester or epoxy (denoted by G), carbon/epoxy (C) and injection-molded carbon or glass short fiber/nylon 66 (I). Three different kinds of woven cloth (plain, satin and semi-unidirectional satin) are tested for GFRP, although only plain woven cloths for CFRP. The ratio of the high strain rate nearly equal to $1 \times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ to the low strain rate nearly equal to $1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$, is nearly equal to 10^6 , in the present series of experiments. In Table 1, D and S denote dynamic and static cases, respectively. σ is the tensile strength, ϵ the strain at the tensile strength, and ϵ_t the total strain at fracture. E_{ab} is the absorbed energy per unit volume in fractured specimens. The details of tested materials and obtained results are shown in Table 1, which also shows the absolute value comparison of dynamic and static values. Typical dynamic stress-strain diagrams in comparison with the corresponding static ones for some GFRP and CFRP specimens are shown in Fig. 4. Figure 5

Fig. 3. Specimen Dimensions.

Table 1. Comparison of Dynamic and Static Tension Test Results of Straight Specimens of GFRP, CFRP and Short-Fiber Reinforced Nylon 66 (5).

No.	COMPOSITE SYSTEM FIBER VOLUME CONTENT	S or D	No. of spec.	$\dot{\epsilon}$ (s^{-1})	σ_p (kg/mm^2)	ϵ_p (%)	ϵ_t (%)	E_{ab} (kg/mm^2)
G1	GLASS/POLYESTER SATIN WOVEN CLOTH 'a'-TYPE, 42.3%	S	3	1.04×10^{-3}	33.1 (1.71)*	4.16 (1.63)*(2.19)*		0.784 (4.58)*
		D	6	1.81×10^3	56.6	6.8 9.1		3.59
G2	GLASS/POLYESTER SATIN WOVEN CLOTH 'b'-TYPE, 40.8%	S	4	1.18×10^{-3}	29.4 (1.73)	4.41 (1.88) (2.22)		0.789 (3.87)
		D	7	2.03×10^3	50.9	8.3 9.8		3.05
G3	GLASS/EPOXY SATIN WOVEN CLOTH 39.4%	S	4	1.17×10^{-3}	32.5 (1.65)	4.77 (1.45) (1.64)		0.904 (2.78)
		D	5	2.12×10^3	53.5	6.9 7.8		2.51
G4	GLASS/POLYESTER PLAIN WOVEN CLOTH 39.6%	S	3	1.05×10^{-3}	28.1 (1.67)	4.37 (1.81) (2.31)		0.721 (4.73)
		D	5	1.79×10^3	46.8	7.9 10.1		3.41
G5	GLASS/EPOXY PLAIN WOVEN CLOTH 43.3%	S	4	0.95×10^{-3}	34.4 (1.71)	3.56 (2.11) (2.42)		0.720 (3.74)
		D	5	1.90×10^3	58.8	7.5 8.6		2.69
G6	GLASS/POLYESTER SEMI-UNIDIRECTIONAL SATIN WOVEN CLOTH 41.9%	S	3	0.87×10^{-3}	47.6 (1.66)	3.49 (2.78) (4.10)		0.980 (8.20)
		D	3	0.58×10^3	78.8	9.7 14.3		8.04
C1	CARBON/EPOXY PLAIN WOVEN CLOTH 'a'-type, 53.0%	S	3	0.99×10^{-3}	56.5 (1.19)	3.30 (0.67) (0.99)		0.995 (1.13)
		D	6	1.86×10^3	67.1	2.22 3.26		1.12
C2	CARBON/EPOXY PLAIN WOVEN CLOTH 'b'-TYPE, 55.0%	S	2	1.13×10^{-3}	53.6 (0.94)	4.63 (0.61) (1.09)		1.42 (0.86)
		D	4	2.07×10^3	50.2	2.84 5.05		1.22
I1	CARBON/NYLON 66 INJECTION MOLDING (short fiber), 30.0%	S	3	1.00×10^{-3}	9.3 (1.22)	2.86 (0.59) (0.70)		0.163 (0.80)
		D	6	0.70×10^3	11.3	1.68 2.00		0.130
I2	GLASS/NYLON 66 INJECTION MOLDING (short fiber), 30.0%	S	3	0.99×10^{-3}	13.9 (0.71)	4.05 (0.42) (0.53)		0.341 (0.39)
		D	7	0.67×10^3	9.9	1.70 2.14		0.132

*Values in parentheses are the ratios of dynamic values to static values.

Fig. 4. Typical Dynamic and Static Stress-Strain Diagrams for Some GFRP and CFRP Straight Specimens.

Fig. 5. Strain-Rate Dependence of Tensile Strength σ_p , Strain at Tensile Strength ϵ_p , Total Strain ϵ_t , and Absorbed Energy per Unit Volume E_{ab} of Straight Specimens.

shows the strain-rate dependence of σ_p , ϵ_p , ϵ_t , and E_{ab} .

These results are summarized as follows: For GFRP, all σ_p , ϵ_p , ϵ_t , and E_{ab} increase with increasing strain rate, for all types of cloths^p and^p both matrices of epoxy and polyester. These strain-rate dependences are defined as strain-rate strengthening, ductilizing, and toughening, respectively. From these results, GFRP is considered to have suitable shock-absorbing ability in high strain rates. On the contrary, CFRP seems to be different in high-velocity tensile behaviour. For CFRP, the variation of the tensile strength and the breaking strains with increasing strain rate is not so remarkable and the strain-rate dependence is slightly positive or negative. When CFRP is used for the structure subjected to impact loading, this characteristics should be kept in design considerations. To utilize the superiority of CFRP in specific strength and specific stiffness in static loading and the above-mentioned merit of GFRP in dynamic loading, hybrids of these two materials or some other combinations of the same object would be effective.

From the fracture appearances of GFRP and CFRP shown in Fig. 6, differences of fracture appearances in static and dynamic tension of GFRP are clear. In dynamic tension, resin between fibers is broken into pieces and blown away, and only fiber bundles are left and show brush-like appearance. For CFRP, the fracture appearance in dynamic tension is similar to the static one and shows simple and rather flat fracture surfaces. These appearances seem to explain the difference of the strain-rate dependence of the absorbed energy. The origin of remarkable increase of E_{ab} in dynamic tension is supposed possibly based upon the increase of the tensile fracture strain of glass fibers and at the same time upon suitable fiber pull-outs. For injection-molded nylon 66 reinforced with short fibers of glass or carbon, definite strain-rate dependence of mechanical properties is not seen in the present data.

Fig. 6. Fracture Appearances of CFRP and GFRP Specimens.

Circumferentially V-Notched Specimens

Using this type of specimen (Fig. 3(b)), fracture mechanical considerations can be made. Investigations are concentrated on GFRP changing matrices and fiber surface treatments. In Table 2, σ_p is the tensile strength and 2γ is the total absorbed energy divided by the minimum cross-sectional area. The strain-rate dependence of σ_p and 2γ are shown in Fig. 7. Although these values of γ are apparent ones, they would be useful for the measure of material properties in another standpoint. The γ values of glass/polyester in dynamic tension are considerably larger than those corresponding values of glass/epoxy. This fact is remarkable especially in plain-woven cloth. Generally the strain-rate dependence of σ_p and 2γ of GFRP shown in Table 2 is positive. The effect of types of matrix resin and fiber surface treatment is large in the γ values and not so clear in the σ_p values. These facts mainly result from the difference in the fracture behaviours as seen in the fracture appearances. Debonding between fibers and matrix, and the following fiber pull-outs become more clear in the order of glass satin- (or plain-) woven cloth/epoxy, glass satin-woven cloth/polyester, and glass plain-woven cloth/polyester. Hence, this type of specimen may be useful to detect the effect of matrix type or fiber surface treatment, which cannot be detected with straight specimens.

Table 2. Comparison of Dynamic and Static Tension Test Results of Circumferentially V-Notched Specimens of GFRP.

COMPOSITE SYSTEM**	V _f (%)	fiber* direc.	S or D	2γ (kg/mm)	σ _p (kg/mm ²)	$\frac{\gamma_d}{\gamma_s}$	$\frac{\sigma_{pd}}{\sigma_{ps}}$
GLASS/POLYESTER SATIN WOVEN CLOTH SLS213-C-A	42.3	L	S D	3.72 22.8	30.1 48.9	6.13	1.62
		T	S D	4.35 24.8	32.1 46.6	5.71	1.45
GLASS/POLYESTER SATIN WOVEN CLOTH SLS213-C-B	47.3	L	S D	3.60 23.3	29.4 48.3	6.46	1.64
		T	S D	4.42 24.6	31.7 49.6	5.57	1.56
GLASS/EPOXY SATIN WOVEN CLOTH SLS213-E-A	40.3	L	S D	3.78 16.3	31.4 47.1	4.30	1.50
		T	S D	3.99 16.2	32.1 46.7	4.06	1.45
GLASS/EPOXY SATIN WOVEN CLOTH SLS213-E-B	51.6	L	S D	5.05 21.9	40.3 60.2	4.33	1.50
		T	S D	5.02 18.9	39.9 56.4	3.77	1.41
GLASS/POLYESTER PLAIN WOVEN CLOTH MS253-C-A	40.3	L	S D	4.05 25.6	27.3 47.1	6.33	1.73
GLASS/POLYESTER PLAIN WOVEN CLOTH MS253-C-B	48.4	L	S D	4.94 44.2	34.6 53.2	8.94	1.54
GLASS/EPOXY PLAIN WOVEN CLOTH MS253-E-A	38.1	L	S D	2.74 20.3	25.8 44.6	7.40	1.73
GLASS/EPOXY PLAIN WOVEN CLOTH MS253-E-B	46.8	L	S D	3.53 20.9	31.3 51.9	5.91	1.66
GLASS/POLYESTER PLAIN WOVEN CLOTH MS252-A	40.5	L	S D	4.02 31.7	26.8 43.2	7.89	1.61
GLASS/POLYESTER SEMI-UNIDIRECTIONAL SCF-E-182	42.2	L	S D	5.48 46.1	50.5 79.8	8.40	1.58

*L: warp direction; T: weft direction.

** supplied by Asahi Fiber Glass Co.

SLS (satin woven)	21	2 (chrome)	A (low)
MS (plain woven)	-----25-----	3C	-----
SCF-E (semi-unidirectional satin woven)	18	(methacryloxy- propyl silane)	B (high)
	<u>thickness</u> of one <u>cloth</u>	3E (epoxy silane)	<u>fiber volume</u> <u>content</u>
	(10 ⁻² mm)	<u>fiber surface</u> <u>treatment</u>	

(a) satin-woven or semi-unidirectional cloth

Fig. 7. Strain-Rate Dependence of Tensile Strength σ_p and Fracture Surface Energy per Unit Area $2\gamma_p$ of Circumferentially V-Notched Specimens. (v : a terminal impact-block velocity).

Low-Temperature Testing

Composite materials are the candidate materials for low-temperature structural use, such as pressure vessels of liquid rocket propellants or liquid helium. Low-temperature structural materials are often subjected to high-velocity deformation, and the mechanical properties of these materials under a combined condition of low temperature and high-velocity deformation must be taken into account in design considerations. One bar method for high-velocity tensile testing is revised to have the capability of low-temperature testing, as shown in Fig. 8. The cryogenic temperature is obtained by immersion of the specimen (Fig. 3(a)) in liquid nitrogen (-196°C) or a mixture of liquid nitrogen and ethanol (-100°C) in a special cold box, which can be split using springs just before high-velocity tensile loading. When the specimen is immersed in liquid nitrogen, the temperatures inside the GFRP specimen and inside the impact block are measured to reach -196°C in about 4 and 10 minutes, respectively. The high-velocity tension test is performed after 20-minute immersion in liquid nitrogen, while the change in the gauge sensitivity constant by the temperature decrease is measured and used to obtain strain values. Typical dynamic stress-strain diagrams for straight specimens are shown in Fig. 9. Increasing of both

(b) plain-woven cloth

breaking strain and absorbed energy at low temperature can be found, although strange at first sight. These behaviours seem to be based upon the combination of suitable local fracture of matrix and/or debonding and fiber pull-out.

Fig. 8. Schematic of One Bar Method for Low-Temperature and High-Velocity Tensile Testing.

Fig. 9. Typical Dynamic Stress-Strain Diagrams at Low Temperatures. ($V_f = 33\%$, $\dot{\epsilon} = 0.66 \times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ or $0.90 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$).

CONCLUSIONS

1. One bar method for high-velocity tensile testing certifies no apparent oscillation in stress-strain diagrams and an experimental procedure for obtaining dynamic stress-strain diagrams up to breaking strain immediately after tests is established.
2. High-velocity brittleness and ductility are found in tested CFRP and GFRP, respectively. This shows composites also have strong individualities in high-velocity tension, as seen in high-velocity brittleness and ductility already found in BCC and FCC metals.
3. Dynamic fracture mechanical considerations can also be made with circumferentially V-notched specimens.
4. One bar method is revised to have the capability of low-temperature testing. GFRP exhibits higher elongation and absorbed energy in high-velocity tension at low temperature.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors acknowledge Messrs. T. Uchimura and K. Ohyama for assistance in experiments.

REFERENCES

- (1) Kawata, K., Fukui, S., Seino, J. and Takada, N., "Some Analytical and Experimental Investigations on High Velocity Elongation of Sheet Metals by Tensile Shock," Behaviour of Dense Media Under High Dynamic Pressure (Proc. of Symp. HDP, IUTAM, Paris, 1967), Dunod, Paris, 1968, pp. 313-323.
- (2) Kawata, K., Hashimoto, S. and Kurokawa, K., "Analysis of High Velocity Tension of Bars of Finite Length of BCC and FCC Metals with Their Own Constitutive Equations," High Velocity Deformation of Solids (Proc. of IUTAM Symp., Tokyo, 1977), Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1979, pp. 1-15.
- (3) Kawata, K., Hashimoto, S., Kurokawa, K. and Kanayama, N., "A New Testing Method for the Characterization of Materials in High Velocity Tension," Mechanical Properties at High Rates of Strain 1979 (Conf. Ser. No. 47), Inst. of Phys., Bristol and London, 1979, pp. 71-80.
- (4) Kawata, K., Hondo, A., Hashimoto, S., Takeda, N. and Chung, H. L., "Dynamic Behaviour Analysis of Composite Materials," Composite Materials: Mechanics, Mechanical Properties and Fabrication (Proc. of Japan-US Conf. on Comp. Mater., Tokyo, 1981), Japan Soc. Comp. Mater., Tokyo, 1981, pp. 2-11.
- (5) Kawata, K., Hashimoto, S. and Takeda, N., "On the High Velocity Ductility and Brittleness of Composites," Proc. of Symp. on Solid Shock Technology-1981, University of Tokyo, 1981, pp. 1-6 (in Japanese).